

Annual Report 2023-2024

Amplifying Voices
Preserving Legacies
Building Futures

Council on
Library and
Information
Resources

CONTENTS

4 Message from the President

8 Digital Library Federation

12 Grants and Fellowships

18 Partnerships

21 Publications

25 Revenue, Expenses, and Financial Statement

27 Sponsors and Members

31 Foundation and Institutional Support

32 Board, Staff, and Presidential Fellows

Message from the President

In 2022 I circulated an essay entitled “Philanthropy in a New Key.” It argued for a more expansive, complex understanding of “sustainability” and “infrastructure,” two key concepts relating to maintaining projects and organizations. Usually distilled to money and technical networks as essential to a project’s durability, the essay countered with the prospect of rethinking these terms to include a socially constructed support system, wherein sustainability and infrastructure would combine and be embodied by intergenerational engagement, a passing along of skills, expertise, intellectual contribution, and societal adoption that would greatly enhance the prospects of a project’s longevity and evolution. The impetus to rethink these concepts arose in part because CLIR’ projects have become more complex, longer term, less bounded, multifaceted, and international.

Lantern slide and photograph of Walter Rosene on an observation tower investigating a Great Horned Owl nest. 1932. Courtesy of Avian Archives of Iowa Online (avIAN), Iowa State University.

Extending our reconceptualizing, this year has been focused on new cooperative working relationships: “Partnership in a New Key,” which can be defined as shared work structured by a functional reciprocity conducive to interdependence. A basic assumption is that broad transformative advancement cannot be achieved by CLIR as a single organization, or by our partners alone, but we can combine mutual interests and purpose with unique professional skills, constituent engagement, and organizational acumen to make progress together.

The diversity of the partners speaks to our complex aspirations: a corporation; an international magazine; a distinguished university that includes several departments, faculty, students, and a celebrated research library; a laboratory focused on advanced foreign language text analysis; and a new climate related research institute at the University of Oxford. Some practical outcomes of these cooperative ventures? New digital resources, robust search and discovery methodologies, and globally applicable training schemas, in addition to transnational curricular development, reorganizations of open and transferable knowledge, and inventive forms of narrative expression and storytelling.

Howard University

The partnership between CLIR and Howard University, an historically Black university, fosters an exchange of knowledge, methodologies, and best practices augmenting and anchoring the Hidden Collections Africa project. The partnership facilitates a bidirectional participation of a plethora of African universities with Howard University’s departments of History, Journalism, and Art History, as well as the Moorland-Spangarn Research Library, which houses one of the world’s finest collections relating to the African diaspora. Existing student and faculty exchange programs will be utilized. The partnership cultivates a new generation of scholars and professionals to preserve and disseminate cultural heritage on an international level. CLIR provides program management expertise, honed through the Digitizing Hidden Collections program.

KITAB/OpenITI

In an effort to expand and enhance the utility and reach of CLIR's Digital Library of the Middle East (DLME) project, we have begun a new collaboration with KITAB, a research laboratory based at the Aga Khan University in London as well as the Open Islamicate Texts Initiative (OpenITI). Our new partnerships provide DLME users a unique, state-of-the-art digital toolbox and a forum for discussions about Arabic texts in completely new ways and to expand the frontiers of knowledge about one of the world's largest and most complex textual traditions. OpenITI's technical advances include sophisticated Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) models that allow KITAB to more easily apply their widely recognized text reuse algorithm to create engaging visualizations of text reuse over time. The DLME provides an enlarged corpus of texts, our network of library contributors, and expertise in pipeline development to allow more institutions to participate in this growing corpus of full-text resources. The community of scholars associated with KITAB will significantly enrich the utility of an increasingly expansive array of digital datasets.

Orion Magazine

This partnership has been created to advance new forms of creative expression in service to the environment, culture heritage, and social justice in the era of climate change. Some of our goals include: developing new methods of storytelling that encourage human responsibility for, and to, our home world, with an emphasis on digital technology and the expressive models it can facilitate; exploring the efficacy of a variety of multimedia techniques in relation to different narrative forms; and designing, implementing, and maintaining new analytical and visualization tools for large scale datasets interpretation. Our objectives also include incorporating often marginalized voices from across the planet, generally with the theme of culture under threat and loss from climate change, and to work concertedly to interrelate the ideas and perspectives of the reading audiences, cultural constituencies, and professional networks of Orion Magazine and CLIR.

Coherent Digital

Employing advanced yet intuitive technologies, Coherent Digital, a corporation founded by a CLIR Board member and based in part on ideas generated by the Coherence at Scale project, provides access to “grey literature” content that is often impermanent. This includes millions of high-quality, statistically rich reports published every year by governments, IGOs, NGOs, and think tanks. Alongside the millions of historical items libraries digitize and upload each year—books, documents, maps, recordings, photos, letters, diaries, and ephemera—this literature provides essential context for historical data with the potential to inform new research. The basic premise of Coherent Digital—making accessible and reusable erstwhile siloed collections essential for scholarship and teaching—is laudable. CLIR is working with the company to identify means of support for the Hidden Collections Africa and Pangia projects through Policy Commons and Africa Commons.

Laudato Si' Research Institute, University of Oxford

CLIR’s most recent partnership, by invitation, is Laudato Si’ Research Institute (LSRI), in the Jesuit-run Campion Hall, Oxford University, a global project that identifies ways academic researchers respond to contemporary social and ecological crises that are deep, interlaced, and systemic in nature. LSRI is framed by principles that include embracing diverse communities of thought and action, encompassing all branches of science and wisdom traditions, with special emphasis on giving voice to impoverished and marginalized societies that consistently face unequal and disproportionately dire consequences from climate-related disruption. A systemic, extended temporal perception and response to climate change that incorporates multiple ways of seeing and knowing will be vital to establish and protect human rights and social justice in the Anthropocene. We are now exploring details of programmatic interaction.

From these affiliations, we believe new communities of practice will rise, new voices will be heard, and new advancements made of significant benefit to our sponsors and members as well as to the public at large. Each and in concert exemplify a principle shared across all of CLIR’s programs: to bring new life to knowledge by design.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Charles Henry".

Charles Henry
President, CLIR

Digital Library Federation

Advancing Collaboration, Innovation, and Social Justice in the Digital Realm

**Research.
Learning.
Social Justice.
Collaboration.
Public Good.**

With 164 member institutions, 9 active working groups, and 30 subgroups, the Digital Library Federation (DLF) community's reach continues to grow.

In 2023-2024, DLF continued to promote collaboration, equity, and innovation across the digital library, archives, museum, and cultural heritage fields. Through its events, working groups, and member organizations, DLF brought dynamic communities of practitioners together to address shared challenges and pursue shared aspirations in these allied fields.

Highlights of DLF’s activities in 2023-2024 reflect the power of a multidisciplinary, cross- sector network dedicated to advancing research, learning, social justice, and the public good.

Assessment Toolkit Release (July 2023)

The DLF Assessment Interest Group introduced the Digital Content Reuse Assessment Framework Toolkit (D-CRAFT), which provides guidelines and tutorials for 10 different methods of demonstrating the impact of digital library collections. D-CRAFT was made possible with support from the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS).

Climate Resiliency Action Workshop Program (July 2023)

DLF’s Climate Justice Working Group received an IMLS grant to launch a free online workshop series designed to empower librarians, archivists, and other cultural workers to take decisive climate action in their daily practice.

Mutual Aid Advocacy (July 2023)

The Labor Working Group and the Archival Workers Collective published “Mutual Aid at Work,” a resource for library, archive, museum, and other cultural workers wishing to form mutual aid networks. Motivated by their observations and experiences during the COVID-19 global pandemic, the authors of this paper offer definitions and examples of how groups can organize to address the issues of precarious employment and limited access to critical resources that often arise during moments of crisis.

DEI Efforts Across GLAM Organizations (August 2023)

The DLF Committee on Equity and Inclusion (CEI) published a comprehensive report providing an analysis and summary of 224 responses to a recent survey issued by its GLAM Diversity Subgroup. The report calls for continued expansion, increased transparency, and ongoing assessment of programs and activities related to anti-racism, diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility within cultural heritage spaces.

Digital Library Accessibility Policy and Practice Guidelines (October 2023)

The DLF Digital Accessibility Working Group (DAWG) released these guidelines to help readers “in overcoming challenges, advocating, and gaining buy-in and support” for implementing accessibility policies for digital libraries.

Anti-Oppressive Facilitation Workshop (May 2024)

DLF organized a workshop on anti-oppressive facilitation for all working group leaders and participants, fostering inclusive leadership practices for all active working groups.

DLF 2023 FORUM

A Global Gathering

From November 12-16, 2023, the DLF Forum convened in St. Louis, Missouri, welcoming 444 registrants from 9 countries and 45 US states and Washington, DC. The numbers reflect significant growth, with participation from three additional countries and four more states compared to 2022.

Program Highlights

103 presentations across various formats:

- 25 panels
- 8 workshops
- 6 working sessions
- 11 lightning talks
- 53 short presentations

Learn@DLF Pre-Conference Workshops

73 participants joined 8 hands-on workshops designed to deepen skills and foster collaboration.

Community Engagement

43% of attendees were first-timers, signaling a growing and inclusive community. 93 volunteers contributed to the planning and review process, with 73 serving on the Planning Committee.

DLF Working Groups

2023-2024

DLF continued to thrive as a dynamic, grassroots community dedicated to collaboration and innovation across the digital library landscape.

DLF's active working groups bring together professionals to share expertise, create solutions, and drive meaningful progress in digital librarianship and allied fields. All interested practitioners whose aims align with DLF's mission are welcome to participate in group activities, regardless of their employment status or the membership status of their employers.

- Arts and Cultural Heritage Working Group
- Assessment Interest Group
- Born-Digital Access Working Group
- Climate Justice Working Group
- Data & Digital Scholarship Working Group
- Digital Accessibility Working Group
- DLF Committee for Equity and Inclusion
- DLF Metadata Support Group
- Digital Library Pedagogy Group
- DLF Project Managers Group
- Technology Strategy for Archives Working Group
- Working Group on Labor in Digital Libraries
- Linked Open Data Zotero Group

Grants and Fellowships

CLIR continued to manage two national regranting programs for digitizing rare and unique content and a postdoctoral fellowship program during 2023-2024.

Cyril George Photograph Collection, sample image of individuals wearing regalia, PO077 . Courtesy of Sealaska Heritage Institute.

Digitizing Hidden Collections: Amplifying Unheard Voices

Since its launch in 2021, with the generous support of the Mellon Foundation, Digitizing Hidden Collections: Amplifying Unheard Voices has helped collecting organizations in the US and Canada bring to light materials that deepen public understanding of the histories and experiences of people of color and other historically overlooked populations.

Institutions can apply individually or jointly for grants of between \$50,000 and \$300,000 to support projects lasting 1 to 3 years. Recipients create digital access to special collections and archival materials in ways that enrich opportunities for research, learning, and the engagement of represented communities with their own heritage.

A second call for initial proposals, opening in August 2023 and closing in November, drew wide interest. An independent review panel selected a representative cross-section of the most competitive proposals to advance to a second, final review phase in early 2024.

Projects nominated for funding will launch in January 2025 and continue for up to three years.

To help applicants prepare final proposals, CLIR hosted a six-part webinar series in March and April 2024. This series, now available as a YouTube playlist, provided step-by-step guidance to applicants planning their digitization projects, helping all participants make decisions about how they would generate, describe, preserve, and promote the use of the digital copies they hoped to create from their collections.

Recordings at Risk

Recordings at Risk is a national regranting program administered by CLIR to support the preservation of rare and unique audio, audiovisual, and other time-based media through digital reformatting. Generously funded by the Mellon Foundation since January 2017, the program encourages professionals who may be constrained by limited resources and/or technical expertise to take action against the threats of degradation and obsolescence. The program aims to help organizations identify priorities and develop practical strategies for digital reformatting, build relationships with qualified external service providers, and raise awareness of best practices. Eligible media may include but are not necessarily limited to, magnetic audio and video tape, grooved discs, wax cylinders, wire recordings, and film (with or without sound).

In August 2023, the program awarded \$644,147 for 17 projects. Among this diverse cohort are projects that will document twentieth-century Native life in America, showcase the evolution of music history, capture the impact of labor and social justice activism, provide insights into animal life, preserve the perspectives and creativity of people from Appalachia, and safeguard the stories of Las Vegas casino workers. An 11th application cycle, open from January to April 2024, saw continued robust participation.

In November 2023, a partnership with Shift Collective initiated a comprehensive evaluation of Recordings at Risk, ensuring it remains responsive to the needs of grantees and aligned with its mission to help under-resourced organizations preserve the fragile and obsolete recordings in their care.

Flooded videotapes removed from containers to dry out. Photo by Leo Shannon. Courtesy of Appalshop, Inc.

Regranting Outcomes, 2015-2024

Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives & Digitizing Hidden Collections: Amplifying Unheard Voices

- 115 projects funded;
- \$28 million awarded;
- 3,365,388 total pages of serials, manuscripts, and other bound volumes;
- an additional 268.7 linear feet and 11,665 additional volumes of serials, manuscripts and other bound volumes;
- 175,107 individual photographs and 320 additional linear feet of photographs;
- 12,041 individual audio and audiovisual recordings and 2203 additional recorded hours of audio and audiovisual recordings;
- 43,179 musical scores;
- 151,885 magazine tear sheet pages, 5763 quilts, 2196 pieces of artwork, 235,585 pieces of ephemera, 10,425 maps, 4,200 posters, and 37,024 pamphlets;
- 60 linear feet of architectural drawings; and
- 238,101 additional pages and 1,482 additional linear feet of mixed archival collections.

Recordings At Risk

- 164 projects funded;
- \$5.1 million awarded;
- 59,582 recordings digitized;
- 107,547 hours digitized;
- 76,374 preservation files produced;
- 142,063 access files created; and
- 104,463 metadata records created.

Fort Bridger Treaty of 1868 Reenactment in Fort Washakie, Wyoming. 2005. Courtesy of Eastern Shoshone Tribe.

Outreach to Potential Applicants

Program officers Sharon Burney and Alyson Pope traveled extensively to share their expertise on grantmaking, funding strategies, and equity in cultural preservation. This engagement has elevated the visibility of CLIR's regranting programs while encouraging less experienced grantseekers to submit proposals.

- **St. Louis, MO:** At the 2023 DLF Forum, Burney presented on funding trends for digital library projects, while the team hosted an exhibit table showcasing CLIR's initiatives.
- **Oklahoma City, OK:** At the annual meeting of the Association of Tribal Archives, Libraries, and Museums (ATALM), CLIR hosted an exhibit table, connecting with tribal and Indigenous cultural heritage professionals.
- **Champaign, IL:** At iPres, the team hosted an exhibit table to engage with international digital preservation experts.
- **Jacksonville, FL:** At the meeting of the Association for the Study of African American Life and History (ASALH), Burney served on a panel, and the team hosted an exhibit table to highlight CLIR's initiatives focused on African American cultural heritage.
- **Boise, ID:** At the meeting of the American Association for State and Local History (AASLH), the team accepted the Award of Excellence for the Material Memory: HBCU Library Alliance Tour podcast.
- **Nashville, TN:** At the Association of African American Museums (AAAM) conference, CLIR hosted an exhibit table to connect with African American museum professionals.
- **Pittsburgh, PA:** At the meeting of the Art Libraries Society of North America (ARLIS/NA), Burney and Pope attended sessions and hosted an exhibit table to engage with art library professionals.
- **Charlotte, NC:** At Queer History South, Pope participated in a panel to discuss equity in cultural heritage preservation.

Staff also contributed to online events, such as a discussion on grantmaking with students from the NYU Moving Image Archiving and Preservation (MIAP) program, webinars on funding for audio preservation, and a panel on equity and ethics organized by the Boston Library Consortium.

CLIR Postdoctoral Fellows 2004-2024

Celebrating Two Decades of Transformative Fellowships

CLIR's Postdoctoral Fellowship Program reached its 20th anniversary in 2024. As the 2020 and 2022 fellowship cohorts concluded their work, they joined the community of 221 fellowship alumni now working in a wide variety of positions in academic, cultural heritage, and government organizations. These individuals' insights and expertise continue to inform the development of CLIR's programs, while their careers exemplify CLIR's long-term impact on the library and cultural heritage sectors.

Over the program's history, fellows worked at 93 unique host institutions, taking up opportunities for interdisciplinary research, assessment, outreach, instruction, curation, and innovative digital projects. Among these partners, the University of California Los Angeles (14 fellows), Johns Hopkins University (12 fellows), and McMaster University (12 fellows) have hosted the most fellows. With fellows representing more than 50 academic disciplines—including many from English (40 fellows), History (29 fellows), Literature (17 fellows), Information Studies (14 fellows), and Anthropology (11 fellows)—the program has enabled subject experts to apply their research and teaching talents to enhance library collections and services while acquiring skills in areas such as digital library research and development, archival practice, and data and software curation.

Alumni Employment Outcomes

CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowship Program alumni have established themselves in multiple sectors, reflecting the breadth of expertise cultivated during their fellowships:

Non-library academic roles

88 alumni (39.8%)

Libraries

74 alumni (33.5%)

State or federal governments

23 alumni (10.4%)

Non-profit sector

12 alumni (5.4%)

Private sector

12 alumni (5.4%)

Other, including self-employed

12 alumni (5.4%)

These outcomes underscore the program's success in equipping fellows with versatile skills and a deep understanding of the challenges and opportunities in their fields.

Partnerships

Much of CLIR's work relies on close collaboration with partners with common interests in preserving and openly sharing information. Two of CLIR's partnerships marked major milestones in 2023-2024.

The Digital Library of the Middle East (DLME) is a federated discovery portal for scholars, students, and the general public interested in the rich history and culture of the Middle East and North Africa (MENA). In 2023-2024, CLIR and DLME technical partners at Stanford University Libraries have focused on community development and engagement with related projects and groups, including the Open Islamicate Texts Initiative (OpenITI), the KITAB Project, and the Middle East Librarians Association.

The DLME team has begun work on integrating datasets from KITAB and on investigating how to adopt data models created by OpenITI to improve full-text search of manuscript and text collections, leveraging cutting edge optical character recognition and handwritten text recognition (OCR/HTR) technologies.

DLME continues to work with institutions, scholars, archivists, and librarians to identify and add collections to the portal. Usage of the site has greatly increased due to outreach efforts, averaging around 12,000 visitors per month. The vast majority of users are from outside the United States; the most popular user language is Arabic.

HBCU
Library Alliance

Empowering HBCU Libraries

A Collaborative Preservation Initiative

With the generous support of 78 CLIR sponsors, a new collaboration between CLIR and the HBCU Library Alliance raised \$85,000 toward preserving the rich cultural heritage of Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs).

The initiative was sparked by a recognition of the crucial roles HBCUs have played in educating students of color since their founding in the mid-1800s. Despite their contributions, many HBCUs struggle with limited resources, particularly for the maintenance and preservation of their archival collections. Against a backdrop of these financial challenges and political attacks against HBCUs, CLIR began working with the HBCU Library Alliance to identify HBCU library-based projects with the potential to serve today's students while fostering a deeper appreciation for the pivotal role of HBCUs in shaping American history and education.

The institutions selected for support include:

- **Lane College, Jackson, TN**, for the digitization of archival materials, including family books, photographs, college reports, yearbooks, rare books, and newspapers;
- **Texas College's D. R. Glass Library, Tyler, TX**, for rebuilding and establishing safeguards for archival collections, restoring college leaders' portraits, and digitizing historical records to increase accessibility;
- **Oakwood University's Eva B. Dykes Library, Huntsville, AL**, for preserving and digitizing the university's audiovisual collections;
- **Cheyney University's Leslie Pinkney Hill Library, Cheyney, PA**, for database subscriptions to support the educational and research needs of students, faculty, staff, and community members;
- **Lincoln University's Langston Hughes Memorial Library, PA**, for creating finding aids, upgrading infrastructure, and enhancing security measures.

CLIR also allocated funds to subsidize sponsorship benefits for 102 HBCUs, ensuring broader participation for HBCU libraries in all CLIR programs.

“HBCUs hold materials and information that clarify and augment the historical record. Through our relationship with CLIR, we are pleased to provide members an opportunity to design a project to advance their libraries, to create scholarship, and to promote teaching and learning.”

~HBCU Library Alliance executive director Sandra Phoenix

“This collaboration touches deeply both heart and mind. Making accessible the compelling stories previously hidden in these libraries and archives brings grace and vitality to our cultural heritage as they inspire a more just and accurate telling of our history.”

~CLIR president Charles Henry

Publications

CLIR publishes reports, newsletters, blogs, podcasts, and other occasional items, driven by programmatic needs, sponsor input, and community interest.

Sharon M. Burney
Host

CLIR received the 2023 AASLH Award of Excellence for the third season of its podcast. This season, titled the HBCU Library Alliance Tour, explores the working lives of librarians and archivists at Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs). The podcast highlights the significance of HBCU collections and their impact on communities. Over eight episodes, host Sharon M. Burney discusses questions of history, identity, and the challenges faced by these institutions with individuals dedicated to preserving and sharing the legacies of these colleges and universities. The discussions also address the role of cultural heritage institutions in preserving Black culture.

Burney, the host of Material Memory, is a program officer who supports CLIR's regranting programs. She is also a respected poet and community organizer, blending historical contributions with contemporary issues in her poetry.

The AASLH has been recognizing excellence in state and local history for over seventy-five years. The organization's awards program celebrates exceptional achievements and raises awareness of impactful work in the field.

“Receiving this prestigious award holds profound significance for me. It has been both an honor and a privilege to actively foster engaging dialogues about these remarkable collections and esteemed institutions of higher education, all of which contribute profoundly to the historical fabric of our nation.”

~CLIR program officer Sharon M. Burney

Pocket Burgundies

CLIR expanded its short-form Pocket Burgundy series with 3 publications addressing critical issues in archiving and cultural preservation.

A Green New Deal for Archives by **Eira Tansey** (July 2023) examines the dual challenges of climate change and labor shortages confronting archives. Drawing inspiration from the US New Deal era, Tansey proposes a public policy framework aimed at bolstering archival resilience through significant public investment, ensuring the preservation of cultural memory amid environmental uncertainties.

Remotely Useful: Practical Lessons for Northern Community Archiving by **Morgen Mills** and **Mark David Turner** (August 2023) bridges the gap between traditional archival practices and the unique challenges of preserving cultural records in Northern regions of Canada and the United States. The guide emphasizes community engagement and offers practical solutions for documentation and preservation in areas profoundly affected by climate change.

The Chinese Archive: A Pocket Manual by **Yasser Ali Nasser** and **Matthew Wong Foreman** (October 2023) offers a timely guide to navigating the evolving archival landscape in the People's Republic of China. Amid increasing governmental restrictions, this manual provides pragmatic advice for researchers, highlighting alternative strategies for conducting scholarly work both in and about China during a period of global academic transformation.

Research and Reports

CLIR released 3 additional works offering insights into cultural heritage, digital scholarship, and data curation practices.

Profiles in Data and Software Curation by **Inna Kouper** (October 2023) is a four-part series that highlights the careers and achievements of 11 former CLIR data and software curation fellows. The work of these and 40 more fellows was made possible with the generous support of the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. The series covers the fellows' experiences and careers as well as their reflections on the challenges of data and software curation.

Learning From and Making Use of Digitized Hidden Collections (October 2023) is a compilation of selected papers presented at the Digitizing Hidden Collections Symposium, a 2022 capstone event for the Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives program. This program issued calls for new applicants between 2015 and 2020. The two-day symposium brought together 135 participants. Presentations addressed the symposium's theme: "We digitized it—what's next? Learning from and making use of digitized hidden collections."

CLIR Fellowships in Data Curation: Cultivating Resilient Networks of Support for New Scholars by **Liz Bishoff** and **Thomas F. R. Clareson** (August 2023) summarizes findings from a retrospective study of CLIR's postdoctoral fellowships in data curation. Between 2019 and 2022, the authors interviewed approximately 70 current and former fellows, supervisors, and program leaders, examining the value the fellowships have held for scholarship and library practice. Over 10 years of the program's history, the field of data curation matured significantly, changing the roles that fellows played in their host organizations. Their roles also evolved during the COVID-19 global pandemic; the report documents how this evolution affected their experiences, organizations, and CLIR's program.

Revenue and Expenses

as of June 30, 2024

Statement of Financial Position

as of June 30, 2024

CURRENT ASSETS	UNRESTRICTED	TEMPORARILY RESTRICTED	TOTAL JUNE 30, 2024	TOTAL JUNE 30, 2023
Cash and cash equivalents	\$1,181,084	\$11,470,953	\$12,652,037	\$11,134,971
Investments	\$516,703	n/a	\$516,703	\$478,018
Prepaid expenses	\$93,062	n/a	\$93,062	\$66,350
Accounts receivable	\$86,610	\$5,554,744	\$5,641,354	\$4,607,550
Meeting Deposits	\$9,798	n/a	\$9,798	n/a
Total Current Assets	\$1,887,257	\$17,025,697	\$18,912,954	\$16,286,889
TOTAL ASSETS	\$1,887,257	\$17,025,697	\$18,912,954	\$16,286,889
CURRENT LIABILITIES				
Accounts payable	\$147,435	\$83,687	\$231,122	\$1,359,284
Compensated absences	\$113,627	n/a	\$113,627	\$118,728
Deferred registration revenue	\$157,639	n/a	\$157,639	\$7,860
Total Current Liabilities	\$418,701	\$83,687	\$502,388	\$1,485,872
TOTAL LIABILITIES	\$418,701	\$83,687	\$502,388	\$1,485,872
NET ASSETS	\$1,468,556	\$16,942,010	\$18,410,566	\$14,801,017
TOTAL LIABILITIES AND NET ASSETS	\$1,887,257	\$17,025,697	\$18,912,954	\$16,286,889

Sponsors and Members

July 1, 2023 - June 30, 2024

^Sustaining Sponsor/Member *CLIR Sponsor and DLF Member +DLF Member Only

Alabama A & M University	Clafflin University
Alabama State University	Clark Atlanta University
Alaska State Library +	Clemson University+
Albany State University	Clinton College
Alcorn State University	Coahoma Community College
Allen University	Coalition for Networked Information*
American Baptist College	Colgate University*
American University	College of Charleston
Amherst College+	College of the Holy Cross
Arizona State University Libraries*	Colorado State University+
Arkansas Baptist College	Columbia University*
Atlanta University Center, Robert W. Woodruff Library*	Concordia University+
Bates College*	Connecticut College
Baylor University*	Coppin State University
Beloit College	Cornell University Libraries*
Benedict College	Corning Museum of Glass+
Bennett College	Council of Independent Colleges
Berea College	Dartmouth College*
Bethune-Cookman University	Delaware State University
Bibliotheca Alexandrina+	Denmark Technical College
Binghamton University	Dillard University
Bishop State Community College	Duke University*
Bluefield State College	Edward Waters College
Boston College*	Elizabeth City State University
Bowdoin College*	Emory University*
Bowie State University	Fayetteville State University
Brown University Library*	Fisk University
Bryn Mawr College Libraries*	Florida Agricultural and Mechanical University
California Digital Library*	Florida Atlantic University
Carleton College	Florida Memorial University
Carnegie Mellon University*	Florida State University+
Carthage College	Fort Valley State University
Casalini Libri	Furman University
Central State University	Gadsden State Community College
Cheyney University of Pennsylvania	George Mason University

Sponsors and Members (cont.)

July 1, 2023 - June 30, 2024

^Sustaining Sponsor/Member *CLIR Sponsor and DLF Member +DLF Member Only

George Washington University*
Georgetown University*
Georgia Institute of Technology*
Georgia State University+
Getty Research Institute+
Grambling State University
Grinnell College*
Hamilton College*
Hampton University
Harris-Stowe State University
Harvard University*
Haverford College*
HBCU Library Alliance+
Howard University
Huston-Tillotson University
Indiana University*
Interdenominational Theological Center
Internet Archive+
Iowa State University*
ITHAKA+
J. F. Drake State Community and Technical College
Jackson State University
James Madison University+
Jarvis Christian College
Jisc*
Johns Hopkins University Libraries^
Johnson C. Smith University
Kentucky State University
Kenyon College*
Lafayette College*
Lane College
Langston University
Lawson State Community College
Le Moyne-Owen College
Library of Congress*
Lincoln University
Lincoln University Missouri
Livingstone College
Los Alamos National Laboratory+
Marquette University*
Massachusetts Institute of Technology*
McMaster University*
Meharry Medical College
Metropolitan New York Library Council (METRO)+
Miami University
Michigan State University+
Middle Tennessee State University*
Middlebury College
Miles College
Mississippi Valley State University
Morehouse College
Morehouse School of Medicine
Morgan State University
Morris College
Mount Holyoke College*
National Archives and Records Administration+
National Gallery of Art+
National Library of Medicine*
New York Arts Resources Consortium+
New York Public Library*
New York University*
Norfolk State University
North Carolina A & T State University
North Carolina Central University
North Carolina State University Libraries*
Northeastern University*
Northwestern University Libraries*
Oakwood University
Obama Foundation+
Oberlin College+
Occidental College*
Oregon State University Libraries*
Paine College

Sponsors and Members (cont.)

July 1, 2023 - June 30, 2024

^Sustaining Sponsor/Member *CLIR Sponsor and DLF Member +DLF Member Only

Paul Quinn College
Peabody Essex Museum Phillips Library+
Pennsylvania State University*
Philadelphia Museum of Art+
Philander Smith College
Prairie View A & M University
Princeton Theological Seminary+
Princeton University Library*
Purdue University Library*
Reed College*
Rhodes College*
Rice University*
Rockefeller Archive Center+
Rockefeller University*
Rust College
Rutgers, the State University of New Jersey
San Diego State University
Savannah State University
Science History Institute+
Sewanee: The University of the South
Shaw University
Shelton State Community College
Shorter College
Simmons College of Kentucky
Skidmore College
Smith College*
Smithsonian Institution*
South Carolina State University
Southern Methodist University*
Southern University and A & M College
Southern University at New Orleans
Southern University at Shreveport
Southern University Law Center
Southwestern Christian College
Spelman College
St Philip's College
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